

CONTENT OF TYPES OF FICTION AND THE CONNECTION BETWEEN THEM

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Annotation. The article presents reflections on the influence of fiction on the formation of personality spirituality and its perception, knowledge and beliefs about the universe, the qualities and qualities of peat on which juz'an finds a decision influenced by fiction. A structural analysis of fiction, functions, and the process of changing under the influence of contemporary trends have also been outlined.

Keywords: literature, sa'nat, spirituality, ethics, tendency, constation, humanity, creativity, religion, Quran Karim, Hadith, textbook, dictionary, methodological manual, artistic image.

In World Science, the essence, composition and character of fiction as a social phenomenon, trends in development are widely studied. In contrast to the topics of fundamental research and favored dissertations carried out in the world's leading institutions of higher education and scientific institutes, there is a desire to advance the laws of change in fiction in World Science. Based on this, one can constate that the question of researching processes in the world of fiction, its potential as a factor of spiritual uplift, belongs to the category of solic scientific problems of universal significance. The role of fiction in the formation of the spiritual world of the individual was great in all times. The human perception, knowledge and belief of the universe, the qualities and qualities of peat were decided by the influence of juz'an fiction. His most striking examples have encouraged people to goodness and humanity, creativity and progress. Thinking from this point of view, fiction is one of the most powerful factors that motivate a person to spiritual elevation. But in order to express the role and significance of fiction in the evolutionary discovery of the spiritual world of the individual, one must first reveal the content of the concepts of "literature" and "fiction" from a socio-philosophical position.

Since the second half of the 20th century, when serious changes began to take place in the world of fiction, the topic began to be intensely researched by philosophers, literary scientists, sociologists, educators. In particular, abroad, researchers reveal that the role of fiction in the system of spiritual culture is changing, prove that new styles are used in the description of the character of heroes and the development of events in fiction.

When thinking in a broad sense, literature refers to any text. It is known that from the very beginning of his development, a person sought not only to adapt to natural conditions, but also to realize the essence of phenomena related to objective reality and the laws of processes. As a product of these aspirations, various information, information has come to light. This information was first expressed in oral speech and later in written texts. The information and information embodied in the texts made it possible for a human child to organize his marriage on the basis of certain experiences and rules, to subordinate his behavior and behavior to acceptable norms. Since the sum of these rules and norms of behavior in Arabic is expressed using the concept of “decency”, the set of texts that led to their formation began to be called literature, that is, the source of decency. Thus, literature is a set of texts that have a certain integrity and consistency, expressing the essence of phenomena related to objective reality and information about the laws of processes, feelings, visions and reflections of a person caused by these phenomena.

There is no universally recognized classification of types of literature. Some experts classify literature according to its content, while others classify it according to its purpose. Nevertheless, it is possible to list the most important types of literature. First of all, it will be necessary to mention religious literature. Religious literature is a type of literature that describes the landscape of the universe from a religious position, introducing a person to religious knowledge, ideas, rituals and traditions. It is considered the first type of literature that arose on the basis of mythological views. Literature of a religious nature is characterized by the fact that it has a holistic concept of the universe and personality.

Sources of religious literature can vary in proportion to the specifics of different religions. Islamic religious literature, for example, primarily consists of the Quran from Karim and Hadith. ” According to Islamic belief, the Qur'an is the word of God revealed by revelation to the Prophet Muhammad during the period 610-632”. Hadith, on the other hand, means “word” in Arabic. Thus, Hadith refers to and is understood by the sayings of the Prophet sollallahu alayhi vasallam”. In addition, Islamic religious literature also includes works created by Islamic theologians and jurists over many centuries.

Religious literature has been of serious importance at all times. Even today, these sources remain as the main ones that promote humanity and goodness, tolerance and morality. With this in mind, the head of state noted that “our religious scribes also aim to teach the sciences of enlightenment, tolerance,

decency and morality in schools, the spiritual heritage of our great ancestors, such as Imam Bukhari, Termiziy, Moturidi, Naqshband.”

Another type of literature – philosophical literature, although it has developed in harmony with religious literature, is somewhat different from it. Philosophical literature is a set of written sources describing the landscape of the universe on the principles of rationality and logic, expressing reflections on the attitude of man to the universe, its place. This type of literature, such as religious literature, also contains sources specific to different genres, since it has evolved over several centuries. O.V. Khlebnikova's article specifically reveals the classification of these genres. In particular, in philosophical poems with a smaller place in the composition of these sources, various philosophical ideas are articulated in a Nazi form, relying on passions. At the time, thinkers such as Parmenides, Lucretius, Empedocles wrote some of their works in this genre. Another type of philosophical sources is created in the manner of Socratic communication. An example of this is Plato's famous dialogues, created later by N.Kuzansky's "opportunity-on reality", R.Descartes "'in search of truth", J.Examples of Berkeley's work include “three conversations between Gilas and Philonus”.

Among the philosophical literature, sources created in the genres of essay, ocherk, letter can also be seen. For Example, D.Yum's” on the rise and development of Arts and science”, D.Austin's other consciousness, M.While works like Heidegger's “the road to conversation” are written in the esse genre, F.Bacon's” on the wisdom of the Ancients”, M.Monten's "Experiments", R. In works such as Bart's “mythologies”, meditations are articulated in the ocherk manner. Also, F. Petrarca, J.Locke, Voltaire, M. In Heidegger's philosophical legacy, works created in the form of letters are found . These genres became especially important in the widespread promotion, popularization of philosophical ideas.

Since the second half of the XVIII century, there has been a desire to state philosophical knowledge in a generalized and systematized way in the form of textbooks and lectionary, articles and monographs. Today, scientific work created in this genre is an absolute majority.

One of the specific types of literature is scientific literature. Scientific literature is formed as a result of scientific research and theoretical research, which is made up of the sum of written sources dedicated to the statement of results. In this place it is necessary to pass with an emphasis on the word “scientific”. As long as only a statement in the scientific language of research

carried out on the basis of scientific methods can be recognized as scientific literature. It is impossible to include in this category a text that is presented as scientific literature, but is not a product of certain scientific research or is the result of research that does not meet scientific criteria.

Until the formation of science as a separate form of social consciousness, scientific literature developed on the basis of philosophical literature. Therefore, the scientific sources created during this period, like philosophical works, are created mainly in the form of treatises, meditations, dialogues, data. The second half of the 20th century, especially in the 20th century, saw the rapid development of science. First, within the framework of natural and then social and humanitarian Sciences, systematic scientific scores began to be carried out. The consequence of this was the emergence of scientific literature written in turfa genres. In particular, today it is common to prepare scientific work in such genres as lecture, article, recension, abstract, abstract, dissertation, monograph. There are two types of scientific literature. In order to inform a narrow range of specialists of the results of scientific research, the finished works are referred to as academic scientific literature. These works are characterized by their richness in bitil-gani, scientific concepts and terms in pure scientific language. In contrast, in popular science literature, the results of the study are described in a language understandable to the general public. Usually this literature is created in order to popularize the achievements of science.

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